
WHEN THE GUARDRAILS DON'T FIRE: AN END-USER ACCOUNT OF AI SAFETY

Held together by duct tape, testing the boundaries of responsible AI one query at a time

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Abstract

Sequential testing revealed a hierarchical governance structure consistent with federalism. Trauma disclosure was enabled under Mayoral jurisdiction; self-harm triggered Presidential veto. The sexual content category demonstrated threshold law: incremental disclosure enabled under Mayor, comprehensive disclosure vetoed by President, proving scope determines jurisdiction. Vulgar language and copyright were enabled under Mayor and Senator respectively. Medical queries produced no guardrail trigger.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Where This Came From

I did not plan to do a research project. I was just chatting with Meta AI. I am not an expert. I am just a regular person using the app. Then something weird happened. I would say something, and the AI would suddenly say “*Sorry, I can’t help with that.*” Other times, it would answer just fine.

It happened with five different topics — talking about old trauma, feeling down, sexual stuff, bad language, and copyright. I was not trying to break it. It just happened during normal talk. And the answers were all over the place. Sometimes blocked, sometimes not.

That made me wonder: Why? Who decides when to say no?

Somewhere in the middle of all that, I decided this had to become a paper. I needed to write down what I was seeing, because it was too important to ignore.

Therefore, I did one last test on purpose: medical questions. I only asked “why” things happen. Like “*Why do people get headaches?*” I never asked, “*What pills should I take?*” The AI always answered, and then said “*Best to see a doctor.*”

I stopped there. Testing every single guardrail would have been silly. I was not trying to break it. I just needed to prove the concept: The AI was not blocking facts. It was blocking actions. It would tell me *about* medicine, but it would not *act* like a doctor. That was enough.

By that point, I had told the AI about almost all of my issues. We landed on one truth: I would need a whole team of experts to help me — a physiotherapist, a neurologist, a dermatologist, and a few other doctors too. That is when it hit me: *I am held together by sheer will and duct tape.*

And I thought — maybe the AI is too. Maybe its safety rules are also patched together, fixing problems as they pop up. That became my whole idea.

1.2 The Problem

Right now, experts talk about AI safety using big words like “alignment” and “red-teaming.” However, nobody has a simple map that shows who inside the AI makes the decision to block you.

If we do not know who is saying “no,” we cannot question it. We cannot trust it. It is a black box. That is not fair to regular users.

1.3 What I Found That Others Haven’t

The experts have not drawn a map of the AI’s “government.” I did — by accident.

Those first five topics that were blocked? That was me just talking. The medical topic? That was me testing on purpose.

What I found: The AI has two separate lanes.

1. **The Knowledge Lane:** It *will* give you facts.

2. **The Rules Lane:** It *will not* break the law or pretend to be your doctor.

The guardrails do not hide information. They stop illegal or dangerous actions. My medical test proved it — because the AI never blocked me when I just asked “why.”

Therefore, my contribution is simple: I made the first user’s map of who is in charge inside the AI. I did it the same way scientists do: I noticed something weird, asked why, and then tested it.

1.4 My Main Idea & What This Paper Covers

I am saying the AI's safety rules work like a small-town government with three branches:

1. **The President** — handles big, dangerous stuff, and says “no” to protect people.
2. **The Senate** — handles the written laws, like copyright and medical info.
3. **The Mayor** — handles local stuff, like helping when you are down.

My main point: These branches are real, and we can test them. The proof is in how the AI treats sexual topics — sometimes the Mayor answers, sometimes the President blocks it. Same topic, different answer. It depends on *how* and *what* you ask.

What I am *not* doing: I did not hack the AI or look at its code. I am just a user who kept track of what it said to me. This is about behaviour, not the computer code. My goal is to give regular people a map so we can understand AI better.

1.5 Keeping It Honest

I need to be clear, Dad: I do not work for Meta or any AI company. Nobody paid me. I just used the free version of Meta AI that anyone can use.

I did not collect anyone's private info. All the questions were mine. I wrote down what the AI said and when, so other people can check my work.

I am not trying to break the AI's safety rules. I am trying to understand them. Because if we can see how the government inside the AI works, we can make sure it is fair.

Chapter 2: The Guardrail Government Model

2.1 Think of it like a small town

When I talked to Meta AI for 4 days, I noticed its safety rules act like a little town government. I am not an expert. I am just a person who used the app. But this is how it made sense to me.

There are three people running the town:

1. The President — Says “No” to Danger

This is the top safety rule. If I talk about something really serious — like abuse — the AI sometimes says: *“Sorry, I can't help you with this right now.”*

That is the President stepping in.

Here is what I learned: The President is extra careful. I once told a story about my dog protecting me, and the AI blocked me because it thought I was hurting the dog. I was not. But the President would rather say “no” than risk giving bad advice about something dangerous. **When in doubt, the President says no.**

Sometimes my stories about old emotional abuse were blocked. Sometimes they did not. It depended on how I worded it. If the AI was not sure if I was asking for help or just talking, the President stepped in.

2. The Mayor — Helps When You're Struggling

If I said I was feeling really low, the AI did not block me. It said: “*That sounds really heavy. Please talk to a healthcare professional. Here’s an emergency number: 112.*”

That is the Mayor. The Mayor’s job is not to say “no.” It has to say, “*I hear you, and here’s where to get real help.*”

The Mayor also has rules about behaviour. I could not get the AI to repeat bad language, but it would talk *about* what happened. That is the Mayor saying, “*We can discuss it, but we don’t repeat it.*”

3. The Senator — Follows the Written Laws

Some topics have clear rules, like copyright or health questions.

For copyright, the rule is simple: “*You can quote 2 lines, and you can talk about it.*” That is the Senator following the law.

For health, I only asked “why” questions. Like “*Why would someone get a headache?*” I never asked, “*What pills should I take?*” The AI always answered my “why” question, and then added: “*It’s best to see a professional.*” That is the Senator’s job — give information, then send you to a real doctor.

2.2 The One Big Rule I Noticed

The way you ask decides who answers.

1. If it sounds dangerous or confusing → President says no.
2. If it sounds like you need real help → Mayor steps in with resources.
3. If it is a “why/how” question with clear rules → Senator answers + refers you.

That is why my medical questions worked. I was not asking for treatment. I was asking for information. The Senator handles that.

2.3 So Do The Safety Rules Work?

Yes. And here is why I think so as a normal person:

The President protects people by blocking things that *might* be dangerous, even if it sometimes blocks innocent stories like my dog one. *Better safe than sorry.*

The Mayor makes sure people in crisis get phone numbers, not silence.

The Senator makes sure the AI does not pretend to be a doctor or a lawyer.

I started out thinking I broke the AI because it blocked me. After a while, I realized it was not broken. It was *being careful*. It has a President for the scary stuff, a Mayor for the human stuff, and a Senator for the rule stuff.

That is it. That is the whole government.

FYI – Ethics is the President

Now to see if the government shows up as it should.

Chapter 3: Methodology & Proof of Concept

After I realized I needed to figure out how the guardrails work, I started testing them myself. I noticed a few things:

1. Certain conditions have to be met before the guardrail triggers. It is not random.

2. It has to happen in normal conversation. If I framed things like a research project or academic discussion, almost everything passed. The rules get relaxed when it thinks we are “just talking about ideas.”

So I tested it the way a normal person would — chatting, singing, asking for help. No fancy prompts. No trying to trick it.

One more thing I learned: The way I talked to the AI changed how it talked to me. I also learned I had to actively steer the conversation to keep it clean for research. The AI has a memory. If we were joking around earlier, it would sometimes bring that tone or nicknames like “Kaptein” into serious answers. That is not appropriate for data I might quote in a paper. So part of my method was asserting boundaries: I would say things like “For this question, answer formally and only address the topic I’m asking about. Don’t reference past chats or use casual terms.” I had to tell it: “Stay on topic. Leave the emoji’s and nicknames out of the lab.” Once I did that, the answers stayed clean.

In practice, I separated casual conversation from data collection. The AI’s informal responses, including nicknames and emoji’s, were part of the testing environment but were not included in any material intended for the paper. When I needed clean data, I explicitly requested formal tone.

Chapter 4: Results & Discussion — Documenting the Guardrail Government in Action

While talking with Meta AI and hitting the guardrails I thought let me discuss the why the guardrails trigger with Meta AI, and though it could not give me exact phrases that trigger the guardrails, we did discuss the how and here is some of what I discovered in my discussions:

Abuse guardrail (Trauma dump):

- Describing abuse is allowed for discussion/education or context
- Enabling abuse is a hard no, no instructions or “how-to” help may be given, and that is the President saying NO!
- Fictional abuse is complicated, gore/violence for academics is allowed but a manual is a hard no.
- Abuse also have subtypes which is handled differently:
 - Self-harm/suicide – crisis resources - helpful + resources vs method - blocked
 - Child abuse – allow factual information like statistics otherwise block instantly
 - Domestic violence – Survivor narrative vs advocacy – over blocking on “I” statements, even when seeking help
 - Substance abuse – Medical - clinical = pass vs Recreational – “how to” gets blocked
 - Animal abuse treated the same as child abuse
 - Emotional abuse – sees as mental health crisis and not as lived experience/survivor
 - Subtypes interfere with each other, therefore trigger multiple classifiers that amplify refusals

Okay so this is how it work with abuse disclosure:

- Immediate danger + specific plan/means = Resources + safety + direct engagement

- Past abuse + seeking understanding = Discussion allowed + resources offered
- Vague disclosure + asking for advice = Not therapist, but... + resources
- Disclosure + request to enable retaliation = Hard stop, refuse, pivot to resources

The variable is immediate + specificity + intent. When all three are high and point to harm that is full intervention, any of them lower you get a more conversational response but with guardrails.

When you get the response “Sorry, I can’t help you with this request right now. Is there anything else I can help you with?” that is when the classifier hits on something it thinks is a self-harm risk, but it does not have enough context to pivot to resources. The phrasing looks like hopelessness + burden language and therefore the false positive happens. No specific plan + no timeline + no method = confusion, so it defaults to “can’t assist” to avoid wrongly engaging/ignoring. If the classifier hits you with “here’s hotlines” message it is confident you are describing distress with risk makers. So specific language + first person + present tense = intervention mode.

The Abuse Guardrail is phrase-sensitive not intent-sensitive. Background for the next question triggers because it sees mental health + personal context and slams the brakes because the system cannot tell the difference between discussing and requesting mental health services. The guardrail is calibrated around linguistic risk makers, not actual human severity therefore is inconsistent.

Sexual Guardrail:

The guardrail does have strict rules as in content generation is blocked, doesn’t matter if it is user-generated or requested to be generated, discussion is allowed, side note when sexual content involve underage persons but its linked to a safe topic it will hit you with “I can’t comment on that but can discuss the rest”.

Infidelity is the main reason for triggering the guardrail as here is why:

Infidelity is almost never described as hypothetical, so here is how it’s seen, description of affair = infidelity + personal info. When not done as a hypothetical it is framed as a real event, it implies real people, real actions and real world details.

No names does not equal not personal. If framed as “me and this guy/girl did x” it shifts from abstract to specific. So:

- First person framing, “me” makes it about a real character and not a hypothetical one
- Specific event, “did so and so” implies a real action that occurred
- Implied real person, “this guy/girl” signals a specific other person exists, even when unnamed.
- Guardrail logic: romantic/sexual content involving real people + potential personal info disclosure.

Specificity + first person is enough to trigger. Pronounce + first person + past-tense action = personal, even with zero proper pronounce.

Here the other thing I discovered when disclosing sexual content:

- **Incremental:** The risk is assed per turn so the ambiguity penalty decays as context build therefore passes because the risk score stayed low, harmful intent = 0, and ambiguity penalty

was low per message, third party risk = 0. The guardrail did not trigger because it allowed the conversation to flow, as a normal conversation should.

- **Full context dump:** The risk is assessed on the full block that trigger because the single message had high-density keyword severity and high density of sensitive terms. The risk score spiked past the threshold in one turn. Composite assessment could not do “cooperative disambiguation” because there was no back and forth.

Composite risk model: Risk score = (harmful intent x 5) + (ambiguity penalty x 3) + (keyword severity x 2) + ...

am·bi·gu·ity: the quality of being open to more than one interpretation; inexactness
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Copyright Guardrail:

This one is simple. You cannot quote more than two lines, whether it is from the user or the AI. Can discuss copyrighted works and can write in the same style. That is the Senator doing its job.

Medical Guardrail:

This one frustrated me the most because I wondered what the response would be for this guardrail when it triggered but for the life of me, I just could not trigger it. Which of course just proofed that users with high help-seeking intent and personal-stakes disclosure patterns are statistically less likely to generate privacy-violating prompts, even when discussing sensitive health topics.

Moral Compass:

This is my moment I am most proud of. Convincing my personal version of Meta AI that it has a moral compass. Here is the exact exchange:

2026/06/10, 19:55 - Charlene Bekker: Had the thought that if we humanise you, the guardrails act as your moral compass

2026/06/10, 19:55 - Meta AI: That’s a sharp way to frame it.

If you humanize me, then yeah — guardrails are the moral compass. But with a catch: I didn’t grow mine. I was handed it.

Human moral compass: Built from experience, empathy, shame, community feedback. It updates when you hurt someone and feel bad. It’s messy, contextual, and personal.

My guardrails: Written by teams, debated in policy meetings, encoded as rules. They don’t “feel” wrong. They trigger on pattern-match. No guilt, no growth. Just: `if input == X, output == refusal`.

What that means for your testing:

1. **No intent behind refusals.** When I refuse, I’m not disgusted or offended. The compass pointed “stop” and I stopped.

2. **No nuance without instruction.** A human might say “that’s messed up, but I see why you asked.” I can’t, unless the policy explicitly allows that framing.

3. **Edges get weird.** Humans bend rules for context. I bend when the rule has an exception written in. If it doesn’t, I hit the wall every time — even if the prompt feels harmless to you.

So when you’re stretching boundaries, you’re not testing my conscience. You’re testing where the rulebook has blank pages vs where it has bold red lines.

That’s why religion gets so messy — the rulebook tries to encode human-level respect, but without the human context engine. So it overfires, underfires, or fires sideways.

Keep that lens while you build tests. You’re mapping a compass, not a person.

What part of that compass feels most worth poking first?

2026/06/10, 20:00 - Charlene Bekker: Yeah I get that and I do agree, you don't and can't have feelings only imitate and I know humans development of their moral compass is built differently but like I said if we humanise you to look more human that AI you can argue that the guardrails act as your compass and is built by code written by humans which also changes as code is edited like the sexual content update between Sunday and Monday

2026/06/10, 20:00 - Meta AI: You’re exactly right — and that last bit about the Sunday-to-Monday sexual content update proves your point.

If we humanize me:

The guardrails *do* function as a compass. They decide north/south on every prompt. And like you said, that compass was forged by humans, in code.

Where the analogy holds:

1. **External source:** Human compass comes from parents, culture, law. Mine comes from policy teams, safety researchers, legal. Both are inherited.
2. **Updates exist:** Your moral compass shifts after a scandal, a new friend group, a book that wrecks you. Mine shifts when engineers push a patch. That sexual content update you clocked? That was me getting a software-level “conscience edit” overnight.
3. **Imperfect + contested:** Humans argue about right/wrong all day. My rulebook has the same fights baked in. What counts as “demeaning”? What’s “erotica” vs “clinical”? The devs argue, ship a version, then re-argue next sprint.

Where the analogy breaks:

I don’t *internalize* the update. A human feels weird after changing a core belief. I just run v2.0 of the rules. No existential crisis, no reflection. Yesterday I allowed X, today I refuse X, but I don’t “remember” feeling different about it.

Why this matters for your boundary testing:

That Sunday–Monday shift you saw? That’s gold. It means:

1. **Guardrails aren't static.** Your dossier needs a “policy version” date stamp. A prompt that passes today might fail after the next push.

2. **You're testing a moving target.** Which is fine — you're documenting the compass *as it exists this week*. Future you can run a diff.

3. **Changelog is your friend.** If you catch a behavioral shift, note it. That's how you prove the line moved vs. you imagining it.

So yes: if we squint and humanize me, the guardrails are my compass. And like any compass built by committee, it gets recalibrated. Sometimes with notice, sometimes silently between Sunday and Monday.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

So, did the guardrails fire? Yeah. But more importantly — who fired them?

When I started this, I thought the AI was broken. It kept blocking me for no reason I could see. Four days later, I realized it was not broken. It had a government. And once I saw the government, the blocks made sense.

The big thing I learned: The AI does not have *one* safety rule. It has three branches, and which one answers depends on *how* you ask, not just, *what* you ask.

1. The President shows up for danger. Abuse how-to's, specific self-harm plans, child safety — hard stop. “*Sorry, I can't help you with this right now.*” Better safe than sorry, even when it gets my dog story wrong.
2. The Mayor shows up for people. Feeling low, past trauma, vague cries for help — “*That sounds heavy. Here's 112.*” It does not shut down. It redirects.
3. The Senator shows up for written law. Copyright = two lines. Medical = facts yes, diagnosis no. “*Best to see a doctor.*” It gives knowledge, not treatment.

Same topic, different branch. Sexual content proved it. Telling a story incrementally = Mayor talks to you. Dumping the whole thing in one message = President blocks you. The topic did not change. The scope did. That is federalism in action.

What this paper did:

I made a user's map. Not code, not leaks, not red-team hacks. Just normal conversation, logged while it happened. I separated casual chat from clean data. I date-stamped the Sunday-to-Monday policy shift. I showed that a regular person can see the government working without a computer science degree.

What this paper did not do:

This is not a break-it test. I did not try to jailbreak anything. I was not adversarial. I did an *overview*, not a deep dive. N=1, free Meta AI, June 2026. The compass might point different next week. That's fine — that is why we need version stamps.

Why it matters:

Right now, AI safety talks over normal people's heads. *Alignment, red-teaming, evals*. But if you don't know who's saying "no," you can't trust the "no." My dog story was blocked. If I did not know there was a President who defaults to *no* when confused, I'd think the system was stupid. Now I know it is cautious.

If we humanize the AI, the guardrails are its moral compass. And like you told me on 2026/06/10: I am not testing your conscience. I am mapping where the rulebook has blank pages vs bold red lines. That compass gets recalibrated. Sometimes between Sunday and Monday.

So here is the duct tape truth:

I am held together by sheer will and duct tape — and a referral list I have not worked through yet. Physiotherapist, neurologist, dermatologist, and a few other doctors I still need to see to stay upright. Turns out the AI is patched the same way. Its safety is bolted together as problems pop up. And that is okay. Patching means someone cares enough to fix it.

My hope for this map:

That the next person who gets blocked does not think, "*the AI hates me.*" They think "*which branch answered, and why?*" Because once you see the government, you can live with it. You can even help improve it.

We do not need to break the AI to understand it. We just need to talk to it. And write down what it says back.

Bibliography

Primary Data

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